

ABOUT THE CONCEPT OF FRIENDSHIP

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Annotation: The article focuses on the research of semantic structure and constituent elements of concept Friendship in English linguoculture. The authors analyze modern fairy-tale discourse in terms of concept Friendship representation and division. Semantic field of concept Friendship and all its constituent elements can be united in three main groups: actions, feelings, relations. This proves that concept Friendship is ideological concept based on associations, emotions, estimations and national connotations.

Keywords: concept, Friendship, linguoculture, core, semantic structure.

Active research in terms of reality conceptualization and categorization processes in different branches of modern linguistics is determined by anthropocentric paradigm within the framework of which language phenomena are perceived in close relation to a human, his/her consciousness and worldview. Concept is the main mode of categorization and major means of conceptualization.

In encyclopedic dictionaries we read: the concept is a multilateral notion that includes not only conceptual and definitional characteristics, but also imaginative, estimative and associative ones that should be taken into account while describing the concept; it is a notion of a human consciousness that provides the formation of universal field which helps to perceive an object involved in spiritual tradition. The concept is a culturally marked verbalized sense that is represented by ranges of its language realizations which create a corresponding lexico-semantic paradigm.

We consider the concept to be a discretionary mental formation that is a basic unit of the intellectual code of a human and has a relatively well-ordered structure. It represents the result of cognitive activity of an individual and society. It also contains complex and encyclopedic information about the represented object or phenomena, interpretation of the given information of a public perception and attitude of a public consciousness to this object or phenomena.

The concept should be explained primarily as a cogitation unit, but not memory one, because its main purpose is to provide cogitative process and

preserve information. The concept has a complex multilateral structure that includes not only conceptual basis, but also social, psychological and cultural component that is not so much cogitated by a language speaker as is felt by him/her. This component includes associations, emotions, evaluation, national images and connotations appropriate to the given culture.

In the history of any national culture the issues concerning such human relationships as love and Friendship always were and now are of primary importance. People try to find out the sense of Friendship, to learn who a friend is and why Friendship is so essential. However, these eternal questions that don't have unique definition stir up a great amount of disputes. Humankind continues realizing the phenomenon of Friendship; self-actualization, life experience and human worldview play are determined greatly by the attitude to Friendship.

Having done some good and let him/her see your strengths, you can conquer Friendship: *You conquered the Friendship of the centaurs when you helped the traitor Firenze escape us.* We "choose" friends taking into account his/her personal qualities and gentlemanliness: *He did feel Cho might have chosen her friends a bit more carefully.*

The seme Intimacy is characterized by the following more detailed semes: "chumminess" and "nearness". Sense of incompatibility of a personality with his/her social position intensifies activity of selfconsciousness and need for an intimate and confiding communication. Not coincidentally this kind of Friendship is associated with youth when a youngster goes out of his family's control, but doesn't come to stay in an "external" world: *Hermione had thrown herself on to him in a hug that nearly knocked him flat...* [6]. *Ron clutched Scabbers closer to his chest* [6]. Mrs Weasley hugged him.

The concept Friendship is multi-faceted and includes semes the meanings of which are conditioned by a complex structure and a great amount of the concept nominators. Firstly, Friendship originates in the basis of common interests and affection, that is why it will have elements of amicable, warm and mutual relations. Secondly, Friendship is a many-sided and dynamic phenomenon: it can originate, develop, come to the different level (admiration and love), break or be rehabilitated again. A social, territorial and activity congeniality, long-term contacts, pleasure of communication and likeness of personal attitudes represent the basis for formation of amicable relations. Covering a big part of the linguistic worldview, the concept Friendship is an ethical concept, reflecting the attitude of one linguistic persona to another.

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